

Equilibrium Studies on Transition Metal Ternary Complexes containing Cyclic Ketones and Thioglycolic Acid in Solution

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The formation constants of the binary (ML and ML₂) and ternary (MAL) complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} (M) with O,O donor cyclic ketones (L) ninhydrin, isatin, 3-methyl-1,2-cyclopentanedione and *N*-hydroxyphthalimide in presence of S,O donor (A) thioglycolic acid have been determined pH-metrically at 30 ± 1° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength in 5% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes are quantified in terms of the statistical parameters, Δ log *K*. The stabilities of the binary and ternary complexes are discussed in the light of different statistical factors.

Very few studies have been made on the complex forming tendencies of the cyclic ketones, viz. 1,2,3-indantrione monohydrate or ninhydrin (NIN), 3-methyl-1,2-cyclopentanedione (MCPD), 2,3-indolinedione or isatin (ISAT), 2-hydroxy-1,3-indolinedione or *N*-hydroxyphthalimide (NHP), which are of greater relevance in different fields of biology and chemistry¹. However, no significant studies have been done regarding the complex formation, stability and relative chelating tendencies of these cyclic ketones in solution, particularly in presence of sulphur donor ligands² like thioglycolic acid (TGA). These studies are of greater importance both *in vivo* and *in vitro*^{2,3}. In continuation of our work in this field^{4,5}, we report here the results of the pH-metric studies of the binary (ML and ML₂) and ternary (MAL) complexes formed by the O,O donors (L) NIN, MCPD, ISAT and NHP (Fig. 1) with the metal ions (M) Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} in presence of S,O donor ligand thioglycolic acid (A) (TGA) in 5% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 30 ± 1° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants (p*K*_a) of ligands and the formation constants of binary and ternary complexes are listed in Table 1. The acid dissociation constants of all the ligands and the (1 : 1) binary

formation constants of the NIN, MCPD and TGA were redetermined under present experimental conditions and are found to be in close agreement with the reported values⁵⁻⁷. The binary formation constants of ISAT and NHP with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} have been determined by analysing the titration curves as described earlier^{4,5}. The stepwise formation of the ternary complexes was confirmed from the experimental titration curves⁴ and also from a number of other observations⁵ such as change in intensity of the colour of the complexation medium, shift in the pH of complexation etc, compared to the corresponding binary complexes. In all the ternary systems (MAL), TGA (A) acted as primary ligand and all other ligands L as secondary ones. In order to have a uniformity and better correlation, both the log *K*_{MAL}^{MA} and log *K*_{MAL}^M values for all the ternary systems are given in Table 1. The influence of the primary ligand (A) on the binding of the secondary ligand (L) and also the relative stability of the ternary complex (MAL) compared to its binary complex (ML) is quantified in terms of the statistical parameter⁸, Δ log *K*, where

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$$

$$\text{or } \log K_{MAL}^M - (\log K_{MA}^M + \log K_{ML}^M)$$

The results (Table 1) indicate that the formation

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS, FORMATION CONSTANTS and $\Delta \log K$ VALUES IN BINARY (MA, ML) AND TERNARY (MAL) COMPLEXES CONTAINING TGA AND OTHER LIGANDS*

Temp = 30°, Ionic Strength = 0.1 M (KNO₃)

Ligand (A/L)	pK _a	Co ^{II}				Ni ^{II}				Zn ^{II}			
		K ^M _{MML}	K ^{MA} _{MAL}	K ^M _{MAL}	$\Delta \log K$	K ^M _{MML}	K ^{MA} _{MAL}	K ^M _{MAL}	$\Delta \log K$	K ^M _{MML}	K ^{MA} _{MAL}	K ^M _{MAL}	$\Delta \log K$
TGA (A)	3.59 10.09	5.95	—	—	—	6.28	—	—	—	7.86	—	—	—
NIN (L)	8.81	3.27	6.54	12.49	+3.27	3.77	6.11	12.39	+2.34	3.86	7.11	14.97	+3.25
MCPD(L)	9.11	3.76	6.71	12.66	+2.95	3.82	5.91	12.19	+2.09	4.38	7.21	15.07	+2.83
ISAT(L)	10.62	4.66 (3.98)	6.36	12.31	+1.70	4.75 (3.92)	5.76	12.04	+1.01	5.85 (4.76)	7.31	15.17	+1.46
NHP(L)	6.45	3.38	4.06	10.01	+0.68	3.43	4.08	10.36	+0.65	3.56	3.95	11.81	+0.39

*Constants are expressed in log units, accurate to ± 0.06 ; values given in the parantheses are 1 : 2 formation constant (log K^{ML}₂)

of the ternary complexes (MAL) is more favoured over their binary complexes (ML). The positive values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that the ternary complexes

are more stable than the corresponding binary complexes. The higher stabilities (positive $\Delta \log K$) of the ternary complexes than expected on statistical grounds⁸, can be attributed to different astatistical³ factors, such as metal-ligand π -interactions, basicity of the ligands, nature of donor atoms and structure of the ligands. In all the ternary systems studied, the primary ligand (A) TGA is a S,O donor in which the sulphur³ can form both σ and π bonds with the metal ions during complexation. Thus, the M-S, d_{π} - d_{π} interactions⁹ increases the stability of the ternary complexes as observed in some similar studies⁷.

Fig. 1

The stabilities of the ternary complexes (MAL) with respect to the secondary ligand (L) followed the sequence : NIN > MCPD > ISAT > NHP. This sequence of stability can be explained both in terms of the basicity and the nature of chelation of the ligand, L. All these ligands (Fig. 1), possess keto and hydroxy groups and bind to the metal ion through O,O⁻ donor atoms, of which the NIN and NHP can bind either through 1,2 or 2,3 donor sites, whereas the MCPD and ISAT only through 1,2 and 2,3 sites respectively. Thus, the NIN and NHP are expected to form stable complexes, when compared to MCPD and ISAT. However, except that of NHP systems, the observed order is almost in accordance with the expectations based on the structure (i.e nature of chelation) of the ligand L. The lower stability of the NHP can be due to its lower basicity when compared to all other ligands NIN, MCPD and ISAT, which are of comparable

basicities. The $\Delta \log K$ values for most of the systems studied are less positive, except for Co^{II} -tga-NIN and Zn^{II} -tga-NIN systems, which are little greater than 3 log units. This may be due to higher chelating ability of NIN. The statistical probability of chelation by NIN through its 1,2 and 2,3 donor sites is more compared to others.

The stabilities of the binary complexes, ML (Table 1) follow the order : ISAT > MCPD > NIN > NHP. This sequence is in accordance with the basicity of the ligands and is almost reverse to the order observed in the ternary systems. Thus, the chelating tendencies of all these cyclic ketones (L) are significantly influenced in presence of (S,O donor) TGA.

The stabilities of the binary complexes (ML) with respect to the metal ion (M), followed the sequence : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, whereas those of the ternary complexes (MAL) as $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$. Except that of the Co^{II} systems of the ternary complexes, the observed order of stability in both the binary and ternary complexes follow Irving-Williams¹⁰ (natural) sequence. The higher stability^{11,12} of Co^{II} (i.e. $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$) can be attributed to the π -bonding¹¹ and strong field^{7,12} nature of the TGA, due to which low-spin Co^{II} complexes would result. In the low-spin complexes, the Co^{II} attains $t_{2g}^1 e_g^1$ configuration, which is susceptible for Jahn-Teller stabilisation¹³ and thus may be responsible for the greater stability of Co^{II} complexes over those of Ni^{II} .

Experimental

The ligands NIN, ISAT, NHP (all E. Merck), MCPD (Aldrich) were used. TGA, metal nitrate salts and all other chemicals used in the experiment were of AnalaR grade. All the solutions were prepared

with double-distilled water, except those of ISAT and NHP which were prepared in 5% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. The solutions of the metal ions and KOH were standardised. The pH-measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength in 5% (v/v) ethanol-water medium under nitrogen atmosphere. The method of calculations and all other experimental details were similar to those described earlier^{4,5}.

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